

Scalable Fabrication of Electrochemical Sensors Via Inkjet Printing of Functionalized Graphene for Pesticide Detection

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Nanomaterials are widely employed to enhance the performance of electrochemical sensors by modifying electrode surfaces. Traditionally, screen-printed electrodes are manually coated with nanomaterial dispersions using the drop-casting method, which suffers from poor reproducibility and limited reusability due to inconsistencies in deposition. This study introduces a novel electrochemical sensor based on nitrogen-doped graphene acid (NGA), deposited via inkjet printing. This approach provides uniform, reproducible, and mechanically stable NGA coatings with significantly reduce material consumption (≈ 3 vs. ≈ 15 μg) compared to drop-casting. The NGA-modified electrodes exhibit enhanced electrochemical performance, as confirmed by a fourfold decrease in charge transfer resistance and a 2.5-fold increase in current response. The sensor reliably detects imidacloprid, a common neonicotinoid pesticide, with excellent selectivity and long-term stability exceeding 110 days. Inkjet printing enables precise material placement and layer control, ensuring strong adhesion and consistent performance even under mechanical stress and in complex matrices like tap water. This work demonstrates the potential of inkjet printing as a scalable and cost-effective strategy for producing high-performance electrochemical sensors.

measurements. Based on terminology,^[1] chemical sensors are defined as “device that transforms chemical information, ranging from the concentration of a specific sample component to total composition analysis, into an analytically useful signal”. In an ideal scenario, such kind of device should be able to respond constantly and reversibly without interfering with the sample. Based on construction they usually consist of two fundamental working units: a receptor and physicochemical transducer.^[2,3] Electrochemical sensors belong to the most explored areas in the scientific research,^[4–6] because they combine advantages of high sensitivity, selectivity, and reproducibility.^[7] They can be also easily miniaturized and fabricated by a cost-effective manner. Such benefits highlight their potential to be employed as portable (even wearable) devices^[8,9] in fields covering the medicinal research as well as environmental monitoring.^[10–12]

1. Introduction

The development of smart devices for the testing of chemical compounds of interest is attractive especially for real-time on-site

Their ability to selectively and sensitively detect the target analyte is given by electrode material and chemical or biological receptor unit placed on the electrode surfaces. Recent advances in nanomaterial research have significantly improved the

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performance of electrochemical sensors, particularly with the introduction of novel materials such as graphene-based materials,^[13] MXenes,^[14] and metal-organic frameworks (MOFs).^[15] Among them, graphene has shown great promise in electrochemical sensing due to its high surface area, conductivity, and mechanical strength,^[16] but it also presents several disadvantages that limit its effectiveness in commercial applications. The key issue is the poor reactivity of its basal plane, which results in slow electron transfer and reduced sensing performance compared to the edge plane sites.^[17] Moreover, graphene-based sensors often face stability and repeatability issues, with degradation or passivation layers forming over time, impacting their long-term usability.^[18] The high cost of producing high-quality graphene through methods like chemical vapor deposition also poses challenges for large-scale applications.^[19,20] Additionally, interference from other substances in complex matrices can affect the selectivity and performance of graphene-based sensors.^[21] To overcome the outlined challenges, we designed and tested different graphene derivatives utilizing the principles of fluorographene chemistry.^[22] This approach facilitates the scalable synthesis of graphene-based materials, allowing precise control over the incorporation of specific suitable functional groups such as nitrile and carboxyl groups for diverse applications.^[23–26] Moreover, comprising both sp^2 and sp^3 carbon atoms, these derivatives possessed sufficient conductivity, making them suitable for applications as sensor materials.

The surface of working electrodes can be modified with nanomaterials through physical, chemical, and electrochemical methods.^[27] Physical methods, such as adsorption, encapsulation, and polymer coating, rely on weak interactions like van der Waals forces and hydrogen bonding.^[28] While simple and cost-effective, these techniques suffer from weak adhesion, poor mechanical stability, and uneven surface coverage, leading to particle agglomeration and reduced reproducibility.^[29] Chemical methods involve covalent bonding, chemisorption, and polymer film deposition, offering stronger and more stable modifications.^[30] However, they require complex synthesis, harsh chemicals, and extensive preparation, which can introduce impurities, alter electrode conductivity, and hinder charge transfer.^[31] Electrochemical methods, including electrodeposition and electropolymerization, allow for precise and controlled nanomaterial deposition with excellent adhesion.^[32] Yet, they demand strict experimental conditions, are prone to non-uniform coatings, and are generally limited to conductive substrates.^[33] Inkjet printing has emerged as a superior alternative for electrode modification, offering precise, reproducible, and digitally controlled nanomaterial deposition. Unlike drop-casting or spray coating, inkjet printing provides homogeneous coverage and layer thickness control, minimizing agglomeration and coffee-ring effects.^[33] One of the major strengths of inkjet printing lies in its precision and spatial resolution, which allow for the controlled deposition of functional materials in complex patterns or multilayered configurations. This level of control enables the fabrication of microstructured and hierarchical electrode surfaces,^[34] even on surfaces of screen-printed electrodes (SPEs), that are difficult to achieve using simple drop-casting, passive adsorption, or in situ polymerization. Several works have demonstrated the feasibility of functionalizing SPEs with

nanomaterials by inkjet printing, including graphene-polymer composites,^[35–37] polypyrrole^[38] and Prussian blue^[39,40] nanoparticles or carbon nanotubes modified with enzymes,^[41] achieving improved electrochemical performance by integrating inkjet and screen printing techniques. Inkjet printing is inherently scalable and automation-friendly, allowing the production of multiple sensors in a single cycle, unlike labour-intensive electrodeposition or polymer coating. Unlike electrodeposition, which requires conductive substrates, inkjet printing works on flexible, paper-based, and non-conductive materials,^[42] paving the way for wearable and disposable sensors. The multi-material deposition capability allows simultaneous patterning of conductive inks, biomolecules, and catalysts, facilitating multi-analyte detection and complex sensor architectures.^[43,44] Additionally, inkjet printing is environmentally friendly, using solvent-free or water-based inks, reducing toxic chemical use compared to traditional polymerization and covalent modification methods.^[45]

In this study, we illustrate the benefits of inkjet printing technology for modification of screen-printed carbon electrodes (SPCEs) in comparison with conventional drop-casting technology, using NGA as suitable candidate for printing. NGA is not only structurally distinct from other graphene derivatives due to its dual functionalization with oxygen- and nitrogen-containing groups, but it also exhibits excellent ink stability and printability, eliminating the need for surfactants, binders, or post-processing steps. As a proof-of-concept, we selected widely used pesticide imidacloprid (IMP) as test compound to evaluate the analytical performance of fabricated NGA-based sensors. The determination of IMP is particularly important due to its widespread application and associated environmental^[46] and health concerns.^[47] IMP belongs to the neonicotinoid class of insecticides, extensively used in agriculture for the protection of crops against a variety of pests.^[48] However, its high water solubility and persistence in the environment raise significant concerns about contamination of soil and water sources. Studies have shown that IMP can adversely affect non-target organisms, particularly pollinators such as honeybees, contributing to colony collapse disorder (CCD) and disrupting ecological balance.^[49] In humans, prolonged exposure to IMP residues, primarily through contaminated food or water, has been linked to potential neurotoxic effects, endocrine disruption, and reproductive toxicity.^[50,51] Results clearly indicate that modifying working electrodes with NGA significantly enhances their sensing performance. Notably, when NGA is deposited using inkjet printing technology, the performance surpasses that achieved with traditional drop-casting technique. Inkjet printing provides superior control over material deposition, ensuring uniform and reproducible NGA layers on the electrode surface. This precision enhances the electrode's sensitivity and stability, enabling it to achieve a competitive limit of detection (LoD) of approximately 4.4 μM when tested with IMP. Additionally, sensors modified with inkjet printing technology exhibit remarkable long-term stability, maintaining performance for nearly four months. Our findings highlight the transformative potential of inkjet printing as a versatile and scalable technique for electrode surface modification. NGA-based sensors, optimized through inkjet printing, hold significant promise for advancing electrochemical monitoring.

Figure 1. a) Schematic representation of the synthesis process for NGA; b) HRTEM image of NGA, along with the distribution of individual elements derived from EDS mapping; c) FTIR spectra comparing the graphite fluoride (GF) parent material, the nitrogen-doped graphene intermediate (GN3), and the final NGA used in this study; d) XPS survey spectrum of NGA, with its elemental composition provided in the inset; e) Deconvoluted C 1s XPS spectral region of NGA, showing contributions from various carbon functional groups; f) Deconvoluted O 1s XPS spectral region of NGA, highlighting oxygen functional groups. The scale bars for all HRTEM images were unified for enhanced clarity.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Morphology and Chemical Characterization of NGA

The morphological properties of NGA (obtained by the synthesis shown in Figure 1a) were evaluated by high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) as shown in Figure 1b and Figure S1 (Supporting Information). Results clearly indicate that sample consists of 2D structures with lateral size ranging from tens of nm up to units of μm , which confirms the potential of NGA to serve as material for inkjet printing technology. Homogeneous distribution of individual elements such as carbon, oxygen, and nitrogen indicates graphene surface functionalization. The synthesis process monitored using infrared spectroscopy showed that after the initial reaction with sodium azide, the characteristic

C–F and CF₂ vibrational modes of fluorographene were replaced by features indicative of an sp²-conjugated network (Figure 1c). Specifically, a broad feature centered at 1535 cm⁻¹ emerged,^[22] while the absence of the sharp peak at 1205 cm⁻¹ confirmed the loss of fluorine during the reaction. Subsequent oxidation of GN3 with nitric acid introduced additional spectral features, including a prominent band at 1715 cm⁻¹, characteristic of carbonyl groups.^[22] The presence of carboxyl groups was further evidenced by their fingerprint bands at 1590, 1445, 1345, and 1230 cm⁻¹, corresponding to asymmetric and symmetric COO⁻ stretching modes, as well as a C–O stretching mode.^[24]

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) corroborated the structural features of the NGA material. The survey spectrum (Figure 1d) revealed an almost complete removal of fluorine (0.8 at.%) and confirmed nitrogen doping (6.5 at.%) along with a

Figure 2. a) Nyquist plot comparing the EIS responses of the bare SPCE (red circles) and the SPCE modified with the NGA derivative (teal circles); b) The modified Randles circuits used to model and evaluate the EIS data for both electrodes; c) Bode plots showing the frequency-dependent impedance response of the bare SPCE (red circles) and the NGA-modified SPCE (teal circles), modified via the drop-casting technique. All experiments were conducted in B-R buffer solution (0.04 M, pH 7.0) containing 5 mM $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$ as a redox probe.

high content of oxygen-functional groups (20.3 at.%), with no significant contamination by other elements. Analysis of the C 1s spectral region (Figure 1e) indicated that only a small fraction (7.1%) of carbon atoms existed within sp^2 graphitic domains at 284.1 eV, suggesting that the oxidation process disrupted most of the sp^2 -conjugated network, introducing substantial defects. The highest number of carbon atoms (44.3%) were present in sp^3 hybridized states, reflecting the high functionalization and defect density of the material. However, due to the complexity of distinguishing sp^2 from sp^3 carbons in mixed hybridization systems, these values should be interpreted cautiously. A significant fraction of carbon atoms (19.8%) was found as carboxylic groups at 288.9 eV,^[22,24,52] while the component at 285.9 eV (14.9%) suggested contributions from both nitrogen doping and adventitious oxygen bound to carbon. Similar number of carbon groups was associated with carbonyl groups (12.5%) observed at 287 eV. Additionally, the peak at 291.2 eV, associated with C–F bonds, was likely overestimated due to overlap with the shake-up satellite of carbon. Deconvolution of the O 1s spectral region (Figure 1f) revealed three main components. The majority of oxygen atoms were associated with carbonyl groups (52.1%). The highly hydrophilic nature of NGA likely resulted in an overestimation of oxygen atoms in the C–O region due to adsorbed water molecules. This was supported by the presence of a component at 536.2 eV, attributed to water vapor above the material's surface, consistent with previous reports.^[53,54] Detailed deconvolution parameters are provided in the Supporting Information (Tables S1 and S2, Supporting Information).

2.2. Electrochemical Characterization of NGA

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was employed first to gain detailed insights into the electrochemical performance of NGA. Figure 2a presents the EIS spectra of both the bare SPCE and the NGA-modified SPCE, represented as Nyquist plots. To accurately describe all the processes occurring at the electrode–electrolyte interface, a modified Randles circuit was applied (Figure 2b). In this circuit, the solution resistance (R_s) corresponds to the resistance of the electrolyte solution, primarily reflecting ion conductivity between the electrodes. The charge transfer resistance (R_{CT}) represents the resistance to electron transfer at the interface, typically during redox reactions. To account for non-ideal capacitive behavior, which is often caused by surface roughness or inhomogeneities, a constant phase element (CPE) was introduced, replacing the ideal capacitor and better modelling the distributed capacitance.^[55,56] Additionally, Warburg impedance was included to model diffusion-controlled processes, which influence the impedance, particularly at lower frequencies, by capturing ion diffusion effects.^[57]

The results clearly show that the R_{CT} for the bare SPCE and the NGA-modified SPCE were 356 Ω and 70 Ω , respectively, indicating a substantial reduction in R_{CT} by more than four times in favour of the NGA-modified electrode. This reduction in charge transfer resistance is also evident in the Bode plots, particularly in the mid-frequency range (Figure 2c). Such improvements can be attributed to the unique structure of NGA, where carbon atoms predominantly exhibit sp^2 hybridization, as confirmed by XPS and Raman spectroscopy. In this hybridization state, carbon atoms form a hexagonal lattice with delocalized π -electrons, facilitating the free movement of electrons across the graphene sheet, which significantly enhances electrical conductivity.^[58,59] Furthermore, nitrogen doping plays a critical role in enhancing the conductivity of graphene derivatives by modifying their electronic structure and introducing active sites. When nitrogen atoms substitute carbon in the graphene lattice, they alter the electron density and shift the Fermi level, which increases carrier density without compromising charge mobility.^[60,61] To further validate these observations, the heterogeneous electron transfer rate constant (k_0) was calculated from the R_{CT} for both the bare and NGA-modified SPCE. Given that R_{CT} is inversely proportional to the exchange current density (i_0), as per the equation:

$$R_{CT} = \frac{RT}{nF i_0} \quad (1)$$

where $i_0 = nFAk_0C$ (where F stands for Faraday constant, A for electrode area, C redox probe concentration), it follows that:

$$R_{CT} = \frac{RT}{n^2 F^2 A C k_0} \quad (2)$$

With this in mind, k_0 was estimated to be $1.19 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$ for the bare SPCE and $6.05 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$ for the NGA-modified SPCE. These findings indicate that NGA-modified electrodes facilitate faster electrochemical reactions compared to unmodified SPCEs. This enhancement can be attributed to the combined effects of the sp^2 -hybridized carbon structure and nitrogen doping, which together improve the conductivity and electrochemical performance of the material. In addition to reduced transfer resistance and increased electron transfer rates, the NGA modification also significantly enhances the electroactive surface area (ECSA) of the electrode. Based on the measured double-layer capacitance (C_{DL}) values obtained from EIS fitting, the ECSA of the unmodified SPCE was estimated to be approximately 0.027 cm^2 , while that of the NGA-modified SPCE reached 0.068 cm^2 , assuming a typical specific capacitance of $40 \mu\text{F cm}^{-2}$.^[62] This corresponds to a more than 2.5-fold increase in electroactive area, which is consistent with the improved interfacial properties observed in the impedance spectra. The enlarged ECSA can be attributed to the high surface area and favorable morphology of the NGA material, which introduces additional electrochemically accessible sites and facilitates more efficient interaction between the analyte and the electrode surface.

2.3. Analytical Performance of NGA Toward IMP Molecule

The electrochemical response of IMP on both bare and NGA-modified SPCEs was evaluated using square-wave voltammetry (SWV). This technique was selected for its ability to effectively suppress capacitive background currents while enabling rapid signal acquisition, typically within seconds.^[63] Figure 3a presents the SWV measurements under optimized conditions performed in B-R buffer (0.04 M, pH 7.0) in the absence and presence of 1 mM IMP. The results demonstrate that neither the bare nor the NGA-modified SPCEs exhibit any significant current response in the voltammetric region of interest when tested without the analyte. However, upon the addition of 1 mM IMP, a significant improvement in current response is observed. Notably, the NGA-modified SPCE shows at least a 2.5-fold higher current response (visible at approximately -1.1 V) compared to the bare SPCE. This enhanced response correlates well with the results from EIS, confirming the enhanced electrocatalytic activity of NGA. Possible explanation reflects the fact that the bare SPCE lacks active reaction sites, whereas the NGA modification facilitates efficient electron transport between IMP molecules and the modified electrode surface. This results in the reduction of electroactive nitro groups ($-\text{NO}_2$) in the IMP structure into hydroxylamine (NHOH) groups.^[1,64] The described mechanism is illustrated in Figure 3b. To better understand the kinetics of IMP electroreduction, cyclic voltammetry (CV) was performed at scan rates ranging from 5 to 100 mV s^{-1} using a constant 1 mM IMP concentration. Figure S2a (Supporting Information) displays the CVs recorded for IMP on NGA-modified SPCEs in 0.04 M B-R buffer

(pH 7.0). The results show well-defined cathodic peaks, which increase consistently with higher scan rates. This indicates that the electrocatalytic reduction of IMP is a kinetically controlled process. The oxidation/reduction of IMP on modified electrodes can occur through either adsorption or diffusion mechanisms. Figure S2b (Supporting Information) reveals a linear relationship between the square root of the scan rate ($\nu^{1/2}$) and the peak current, with a correlation coefficient (R^2) of 0.9929. These results confirm that the electrochemical reduction of IMP on NGA-modified SPCEs is diffusion-controlled.^[64] Based on the rapid development of the electrochemical signal during SWV measurements, the response time of the NGA-modified sensor can be estimated in the range of 5–10 s. This fast and reproducible response is consistent with the diffusion-controlled nature of the electrochemical process and the efficient electron transfer facilitated by the NGA layer. Such a short response time highlights the practical potential of the NGA-modified electrodes for real-time pesticide monitoring applications, where rapid and reliable detection is essential.

Furthermore, inkjet printing technology was employed to enhance the electrochemical performance of NGA-modified sensors. The process of NGA deposition via inkjet printing is illustrated in Figure 3c. As discussed in the Introduction, inkjet printing offers significant advantages over conventional drop-casting, including higher precision and more uniform material deposition on electrode surfaces. This technique also effectively addresses common drawbacks such as coffee-ring formation, electrode fouling, and material cracking.^[29,45,65] To validate these benefits, a series of comparative experiments was performed (Figures 3d–f). SWV results (Figure 3d) demonstrated that SPCEs modified by both drop-casting ($20 \mu\text{L}$ of a 0.75 mg mL^{-1} suspension) and inkjet printing (5 layers) produced comparable current responses when tested with 1 mM IMP. Notably, this similarity in performance is remarkable considering the substantial difference in the amount of NGA deposited: approximately $15 \mu\text{g}$ per electrode via drop-casting, versus only $\approx 3 \mu\text{g}$ via inkjet printing. EIS analysis (Figure S3, Supporting Information) revealed that the ECSA of the inkjet-printed electrode (0.143 cm^2) was more than twice that of the drop-casted electrode (0.068 cm^2). This finding indicates that the better utilization of active sites in the inkjet-printed films compensates for the lower material loading, enabling comparable analytical performance. However, increasing the number of inkjet-printed layers to 10 led to a further decline in current response, suggesting that five printed layers offer optimal sensor performance. This decrease is likely due to the formation of a thicker, denser NGA layer that acts as a diffusion barrier for the analyte. Such behaviour aligns with the properties of the NGA-ink, which contains fine graphene flakes ($<450 \text{ nm}$), promoting uniform and consistent coverage on the electrode surface (Figure 3e). The strong adhesion of the inkjet-printed NGA layer is also evident in the insets of Figure 3e, where the material remains firmly attached even after electrolyte removal using a plastic pipette or filter paper. To assess mechanical stability, both drop-casted and inkjet-printed NGA-modified electrodes were subjected to continuous stirring in water for 24 h. Post-stirring SWV measurements and SEM analyses (Figure 3f,e) indicated that the inkjet-printed sensors retained their performance and morphology, demonstrating excellent mechanical robustness. In contrast, drop-casted electrodes exhibited a

Figure 3. a) SWVs comparing the electrochemical responses of bare SPCE (red line) and NGA-modified SPCE (teal line) in the absence and presence of 1 mM IMP; b) Proposed mechanism for the electroreduction of IMP on the NGA-modified SPCE; c) mechanism of SPCE modification with NGA using the inkjet printing technology; d) SWVs comparing the performance of SPCEs modified with NGA using inkjet printing and drop-casting techniques for detecting 1 mM IMP; e) SEM images of bare SPCE, SPCE modified with NGA by drop-casting method, SPCE modified with NGA by inkjet printing technology and SEM image of SPCE modified with NGA after the 24 H of stirring in water; f) SWVs comparing the performance of SPCEs modified with NGA using both drop-casting and inkjet printing techniques after 24 H of stirring in water. All experiments were performed in B-R buffer solution (0.04 M, pH 7.0). The scale bars for all SEM images were unified for enhanced clarity.

noticeable decline in current response, likely due to partial loss of the NGA layer during mechanical stirring.

SPCEs modified with five layers of inkjet-printed NGA exhibited only a modest ($\approx 10\%$) reduction in current response compared to drop-casting, while providing a more homogeneous and smoother surface morphology. To investigate differences in

material distribution across the electrode surface, both drop-casted and inkjet-printed variants were comparatively analyzed using microscopic techniques (Figure 4a–f). SEM images of the drop-casted sample (Figure 4a) revealed the formation of coffee-ring and material cracking, in contrast to the uniform coverage observed in the inkjet-printed modification (Figure 4b). These

Figure 4. a) Schematic illustration of the drop-casting process and corresponding SEM images of SPCEs modified using this technique. b) Schematic illustration of the inkjet printing process and corresponding SEM images of SPCEs modified via inkjet printing. c) Photo of SPCE electrode subjected to profilometry measurement. d) Profilometry measurements of SPCEs modified by drop-casting and inkjet printing, including corresponding variance in distribution of surface height. e) AFM images of SPCEs modified by drop-casting and inkjet printing, including corresponding surface height profiles. f) 3D topography images of SPCEs modified by drop-casting and inkjet printing. All scale-bars were unified to possess better visibility.

morphological differences were further supported by profilometry (Figure 4c,d), which showed a concave height profile across the working electrode area for the drop-casted layer, consistent with material accumulation at the edges. In contrast, the inkjet-printed film exhibited a narrower height distribution, as reflected by a lower interquartile range, tighter whisker span, and fewer outliers. AFM analysis (Figure 4e) was employed to quantify the surface roughness, with a root mean square roughness (R_q) value of $0.216 \mu\text{m}$ for the inkjet-modified electrode, significantly lower than the $0.417 \mu\text{m}$ observed for the drop-casted surface. This reduction quantitatively confirms the enhanced uniformity and

controlled film formation achieved through inkjet printing. Finally, quantitative 3D surface topography (Figure 4f) further supported the visual and statistical differences in particle distribution across the electrode surfaces.

The analytical performance of inkjet-printed sensor toward IMP determination is illustrated in Figure 5a–d. Figure 5a shows the SW response of IMP across a range of IMP concentrations ($5\text{--}400 \mu\text{M}$) recorded at optimized SW conditions. Results clearly show that the cathodic peak current increased linearly with higher IMP concentrations, allowing the determination of key sensor parameters such as the LoD and sensitivity. Using the

Figure 5. a) SWV response of NGA-modified SPCE in the presence of IMP at concentrations ranging from 5 to 400 μM , inset: calibration curve for the sensor; b) SWV results from an interference study with nitrobenzene, hexachlorobenzene, sodium nitrite and sodium nitrate to evaluate the selectivity of the NGA-modified SPCE; c) SWVs reflecting the stability test of inkjet-printed NGA-modified SPCEs over a period of approximately four months; d) SWVs reflecting the stability test of NGA-drop casted SPCEs over a period of 15 days. All experiments were performed in B-R buffer solution (0.04 M, pH 7.0).

standard deviation of the blank electrode response (s_{x0}) without IMP and the slope of the calibration plot (b), the LoD was calculated as 4.42 μM using the equation:^[66]

$$LoD = 3.9 \frac{s_{x0}}{b} \quad (3)$$

The sensitivity (S) of the NGA-modified SPCE was calculated from the slope of the linear regression and the active area of the modified electrode using the equation:^[1]

$$S = b/A \quad (4)$$

The resulting sensitivity equaled to 0.4 $\mu\text{A } \mu\text{M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. Additionally, the sensor demonstrated a linear range for IMP detection between 5 and 400 μM . These parameters were compared with previously reported numbers in the relevant literature related to electrochemical determination of IMP and are summarized in Table S3 (Supporting Information).^[67–74] The results

clearly indicate that NGA-modified sensors offer a significantly improved linear detection range while maintaining comparable performance in terms of the LoD.

For practical applications, the selectivity of the NGA sensor was evaluated using SWV in the presence of potential interfering chemical compounds including NaNO_2 , NaNO_3 and pesticides such as hexachlorobenzene and nitroaromatics, including nitrobenzene. As shown in Figure 5b, hexachlorobenzene, NaNO_2 and NaNO_3 at a concentration of 1 mM did not interfere with the sensor response within the region of interest. Nitrobenzene (1 mM) produced a signal similar to IMP but at a potential approximately 400 mV lower than the cathodic response of IMP. Common ions such as Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Cl^- , which are part of common buffers, did not significantly influence the current response, as confirmed by earlier experiments.

The stability and reproducibility of the NGA-modified sensor were assessed through repetitive SWV measurements over 113 days. Fifteen SPCEs modified via inkjet printing were stored in

a desiccator and tested weekly in triplicate (Figure 5c). The results showed that the sensor's response remained almost constant, with a standard deviation below 5%, highlighting both the excellent stability of the NGA material and the reproducibility of the inkjet printing fabrication process. These results surpass those reported in previous studies, where the proposed sensors either exhibited lower material stability or lacked stability data altogether.^[1,68,71,74,75] To further support these results, a comparative study was conducted using the drop-casting method. Eighteen SPCEs were modified with NGA via drop-casting, stored under the same conditions for two weeks, and tested using the same protocol (Figure 5d). While the NGA material again exhibited satisfactory stability, the standard deviation of the drop-casted sensors increased to approximately 8%. This outcome was anticipated, as drop-casting typically results in a less uniform material distribution due to the broad size range of NGA flakes (from hundreds of nanometers to several micrometers). Consequently, each drop-casted SPCE presents a different effective surface area for electron exchange, leading to greater variability in sensor performance and thus a higher standard deviation among individual electrodes.

The performance of the fabricated NGA sensor was validated using water sample from the local tap water and local well supply. Water samples were diluted with B-R buffer (0.04 M, pH 7.0) in a 1:1 ratio to maintain a pH of approximately 7, ensuring consistent working conditions. Changes in current and potential were monitored using SWV with 1 mM IMP as the analyte, as shown in Figure S4 (Supporting Information). The results indicated only minimal changes in current response and a slight shift in potential for the tap water sample compared to the response in B-R buffer. These findings highlight the importance of pre-calibrating the sensors under specific sample conditions to account for potential interference and minimize false-positive responses during the evaluation of NGA-based sensors.

3. Conclusion

In this study, we demonstrated the successful development of a high-performance electrochemical sensor based on NGA, utilizing inkjet printing as a precise and scalable method for electrode surface modification. Compared to traditional drop-casting, inkjet printing enabled the deposition of highly uniform NGA layers with significantly reduced material consumption while preserving – or even enhancing – electrochemical performance. The NGA-modified sensors exhibited competitive analytical characteristics for the detection of IMP, achieving a low limit of detection (4.42 μM), high sensitivity (0.4 $\mu\text{A } \mu\text{M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$), and a broad linear detection range (5–400 μM). These sensors also demonstrated high selectivity against potential interferents and exceptional long-term stability, maintaining consistent performance over 113 days with minimal variation. Overall, the combination of inkjet printing technology with graphene derivative-based material offers a promising platform for the fabrication of cost-effective, scalable, and reliable electrochemical sensors. These findings pave the way for the development of next-generation portable and disposable sensing devices.

4. Experimental Section

Reagents and Materials: Graphite fluoride (>61 wt.% F), and *N,N*-Dimethylformamide (DMF, $\geq 98\%$) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Acetone (pure) and ethanol (absolute) were purchased from Penta, Czech Republic. All chemicals were used without further purification. Ultrapure water ($18 \text{ M}\Omega \text{ cm}^{-1}$) was used for washings.

Synthetic Protocol and Characterization of NGA Derivative—Synthesis of NGA and Preparation of NGA-ink: The synthesis of the NGA material was performed using a wet chemistry approach starting from fluorographene, as illustrated in Figure 1a. Initially, graphite fluoride was dispersed in DMF and subjected to sonication to yield a fluorographene dispersion. This dispersion was subsequently reacted with sodium azide at 130 °C, producing GN3, a nitrogen-doped graphene derivative.^[76] Following filtration and washing, the GN3 product was oxidized using 45 wt.% aqueous nitric acid. The resulting NGA material was recovered by filtration and subjected to further purification via dialysis of its aqueous dispersion. NGA-ink was prepared as follows: freshly synthesized NGA material was subjected to sonication for 6 h and then filtered through a 450 nm filter. The pH of the prepared ink was 3.7 due to hydrolysis of the presence of the carboxylic groups on the material. The final concentration of solid component in the NGA-ink was 2.0 mg mL^{-1} . Other ink-related physical parameters such as surface tension and viscosity corresponded well to the previously published work.^[45]

Synthetic Protocol and Characterization of NGA Derivative—Microscopic and Spectroscopic Techniques: Microscopic and spectroscopic analyses of NGA derivative were conducted using following instruments: high-resolution transmission electron microscope (HRTEM) images were conducted by HRTEM TITAN 60–300 microscope with an X-FEG type emission gun, operating at 300 kV. Scanning transmission electron microscopy high-angle annular darkfield imaging (STEM-HAADF) analysis for EDS (energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy) elemental mapping on the products was performed with a FEI Titan HRTEM microscope operating at 80 kV. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images were obtained by Jeol-7900F SEM microscope and Scios 2 Dual Beam (ThermoFisher SCIEN-TIFIC) with accelerating voltage of 5kV. For this analysis, a droplet of an aqueous dispersion of the material under study with a concentration of $\sim 0.1 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$ was deposited on a carbon-coated copper grid and dried at room temperature for 24 h or the samples were placed on a double-sided carbon tape on the aluminium holder and coated by approximately 10 nm gold layer (20 mA, 36 s). AFM images were obtained by SPM NTEGRA (NT-MDT) in semi-contact mode with HA-NC tips. Profilometry surface measurements were performed using Dektak XT stylus profilometer (Bruker) with stylus width of 12.5 μm and low stylus force of 3 mg. For quantitative 3D surface topography measurements, a LEXT OLS5000 3D laser measuring microscope (Olympus) with 4K scanning technology was used.

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra were obtained with an iS5 FTIR spectrometer by Thermo Nicolet, which included a Smart Orbit ATR accessory featuring a ZnSe crystal. For this, 20 μL of the sample dispersed in distilled water was applied to the ZnSe crystal and allowed to air-dry. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were performed using a Nexsa G2 spectrometer from Thermo Fisher Scientific, equipped with an Al *K* α radiation source. The resulting data were analyzed with Advantage software.

Electrochemical Measurements: All electrochemical experiments were conducted using a Metrohm Autolab PGSTAT128N potentiostat (MetrohmAutolab B.V., Netherlands) controlled by the NOVA software package (version 1.11.2). The experimental setup employed a three-electrode configuration, utilizing commercially available Metrohm DropSens SPCE. Metrohm DropSens SPCEs consist of the working and counter electrodes made from carbon ink, and reference electrode made from Ag ink. Modification process of SPCEs was performed as follows: a) drop-casting method included pipetting of 20 μL droplet of a powder suspension (0.75 mg mL^{-1}) on the SPCE surface, and it was subsequently allowed to dry at room temperature, forming a thin film. b) modification of SPCE via inkjet printing technology was conducted using Fujifilm Dimatix Materials Printer, model DMP-2850 equipped with Dimatix Drop Manager v3.2.4.2 software. Samba cartridges featuring piezoelectric printheads

with 12 jets and a native drop volume of 2.4 pL were used. All layers were printed in high 2540 dpi resolution, which corresponds to 1.7° head angle and drop spacing of 10 μm. The cartridge temperature was left at the default setting of 28 °C, and the platen heating was turned off, keeping the substrate temperature at ambient level. The cartridge print height was set to be 1 mm. Before printing NGA layer, the jetting waveform and the voltage applied to the jets were optimized to form spherical drops without ligaments or satellite droplets during jetting. Only one jet at a time was used to ensure maximum printing quality. After each layer was printed, there was a 10 min pause to allow the printed ink to dry completely. All electrochemical experiments were carried out at room temperature (22 ± 2 °C) in Britton-Robinson (B-R) buffer solution (0.04 M, pH 7.0).

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

MO has share in biosimulation company InSiliBio (France) and supercaps company ATOMIVER (Czechia).

Data Availability Statement

Data are available via ZENODO repository at <https://zenodo.org/records/17182898>.

Keywords

electrode modification, graphene derivative, imidacloprid, inkjet printing

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